

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

Search for seedborne endophytic fungi in rice

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A search was made for *Acremonium* spp. endophytes in the seeds of *Oryza* and related species. These endophytes occur in a symbiotic relationship with many grasses where they assist in the growth and persistence of their host. They are beneficial because the chemicals they produce make the grass more tolerant of drought, produce more tillers and seed, and enhance resistance to some pests and diseases. Infected grasses are symptomless and transmission of the fungus is only through mycelium in the seed. Usually all seeds from an infected plant contain mycelium.

The benefits could be considerable if such a fungus was present in rice. Seeds in the IRRI germplasm collection from

20 species of *Oryza* and 5 species in related genera collected from 31 countries were examined for the presence of endophyte mycelium. Seeds of *O. glaberrima*, *O. glumaepatula*, *O. rhizomatis*, and *O. schlechteri* were not available for testing. Seeds were softened by soaking overnight in 5% sodium hydroxide, then washed in water and boiled for 2 min in Garner's solution (50 ml lactic acid, 0.325 g aniline blue, 100 ml water). Seeds were then deglumed, squashed on a microscope slide, mounted in aniline blue, and examined with a microscope for the presence of endophyte mycelium. Single seeds from 20 to 100 plants were examined where possible, but for a few species, only 5-10 seeds were available. The species examined and the countries from where the seeds were collected are listed (see table). None were infected with endophyte mycelium.

It is unlikely that species of rice and related genera are infected with *Acremonium* endophytes. However, the possibility that some species may contain this endophyte cannot be ruled out entirely. ■

Species examined for the presence of *Acremonium* endophytes.

Species	Country of origin
<i>Oryza alta</i>	Brazil, India
<i>O. australiensis</i>	Australia
<i>O. barthii</i>	Guinea, Mali, Sierra Leone
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	Mali, Sierra Leone
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	Sri Lanka
<i>O. grandiglumis</i>	Brazil
<i>O. granulata</i>	India, Malaysia, Nepal
<i>O. latifolia</i>	Costa Rica, Guatemala
<i>O. longiglumis</i>	Indonesia
<i>O. longistaminata</i>	Benin, Côte d' Ivoire, Nigeria, Sierra Leone
<i>O. malampuzhaensis</i>	India
<i>O. meridionalis</i>	Australia
<i>O. meyeriana</i>	Malaysia
<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines
<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh, Cambodia, India, Myanmar, Sri Lanka, Taiwan-China, Thailand
<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia, Myanmar, Thailand
<i>O. punctata</i>	Cameroon, Chad, Ghana, India, Kenya, Nigeria, Tanzania, Zaire
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	Thailand
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Bangladesh, China, India, Malaysia, Papua New Guinea, Taiwan-China, Thailand
<i>O. sativa</i>	Bangladesh, India, Malaysia, Taiwan-China
<i>Chikusichloa</i> sp.	Japan
<i>Hygroryza aristata</i>	Sri Lanka
<i>Leersia perrieri</i>	Madagascar
<i>L. tisseranti</i>	Guinea
<i>Rhynchoryza subulata</i>	Argentina

Genetics

Genetic variation in chemical composition and digestibility of nutrients in rice straw

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The chemical composition and nylon bag organic matter digestibility (NBOMD) were determined for 24 straw samples from 21 varieties (Table 1). Twelve were grown in an agronomic trial in 1988 and 12 in a plant breeding trial in 1989. Sita, Pant Dhan 4, and Saket 4 were used in both years. All varieties were hand-harvested at 6-7 cm above the ground. Varieties were grouped according to their

Table 1. Rice varieties grouped according to nylon bag organic matter digestibility where A = high, B = medium, and C = low. 1988-89.

Group A	Group B	Group C
Saket 4 (2) IET8580	Narendra 2 Pant Dhan 4 (2)	Sita (2) VL 8
Narendra 118 Pant Dhan 6 UPR79-123 Manhar	Ratna Sarju 52 IR8 IR24	IET9362
Jaya	VPR83-34 IET8111 IET8110 UPR-80-120 Govind	

NBOMD where A = high, B = medium, and C = low (Table 2).

After 72 h of incubation in fistulated rumens of cattle, the NBOMD varied

Table 2. Chemical composition (g/kg dry matter) and digestibility of nutrients (%) in rice straw. 1988-89.^a

Nutrient	NBOMD group		
	A High	B Medium	C Low
<i>Chemical composition</i>			
NDF	692	729	728
Hemicellulose	231	251	250
Cellulose	298	324	309
Crude protein	54	48	46
<i>Digestibility</i>			
Organic matter	53	50	45
Hemicellulose	52	52	45
Cellulose	48	48	42
	46	44	39

^aFigures are average values.

from 443 to 548 g/kg. A averaged 530; B, 501; and C, 453. Chemical composition in B and C was similar, so